

Influence of Disease Severity on Psychological Adjustment of Patients with Myasthenia Gravis

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May20 , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 25, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Myasthenia Gravis,Disease Severity, Adjustment</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5598665</p>	<p><i>Objectives:</i>To translate MG-ADL in Urdu and to estimate the impact of symptom severity on psychological adjustment of patients with MG.</p> <p><i>Method:</i> It was a correlational cross-sectional research. Study was conducted in May 2020 to June 2021. The data was obtained with the assistance of Pakistan Myasthenia Welfare Organization (PMWO). Patients were approached individually and consent to participate in study was taken from each patient. Purposive sampling technique was used; all diagnosed patients with duration of illness greater than 1 year were included in the present research. Those patients who do not fall in this criterion were excluded from study.</p> <p><i>Results:</i> Data was collected from total of 270 patients, of them 133(52%) were female and (48%) were male with age range between 20 to 80 years. The MG-ADL translated version showed Chronbach's alpha of 0.875. CFA presented good fit of the model to data and all items loaded well on their latent factor (CFI= 0.95,IFI= 0.95,NFI=0.92,RMSEA=0.08). Negative and significant relationship was found between disease severity and psychological adjustment ($\beta = -0.869, p < 0.001$).</p> <p><i>Conclusion:</i> The MG- ADL Urdu version showed good psychometric properties and it was found to be a reliable and valid measure. MG-ADL is recommended to be used in research and clinical setting. Symptom severity of Myasthenia gravis has negative impact on psychological adjustment of patients. Mental and psychological well-being should be a prime focus of clinicians dealing with such kind of chronic and disabling conditions.</p>

Introduction

Myasthenia gravis is enduring neuromuscular illness regarded as fluctuating weakness of the skeletal muscles (Jeong et al., 2018). Prevalence estimates of MG vary in published literature however; the prevalence rate of 35,000 to 60,000 or at least 14 to 20 per 1000,000 persons in United States was reported by myasthenia gravis foundation of America (Bacci, Coyne, Poon, Harris, & Boscoe, 2019). It is an autoimmune neuromuscular junction disorder with varying degree of fatigue and weakness in different muscle groups and this weakness elevates during activity and it gets better after rest. Symptoms may include weakness in arms, legs, hands fingers and neck, shortness of breath, weakness of eye muscles, difficulty in swallowing and impaired speech (Cioncoloni et al., 2016). Currently there is no cure of myasthenia gravis, symptomatic treatments are effective in most cases but have severe side effects (Wang et al., 2018).

Neuromuscular illnesses have a wide range of influence on many areas of life. People with a chronic disease undergo continuous psychological and behavioral adaptations in relation to the various changes imposed by their disease (Pierobon, Giardini, Callegari, & Majani, 2011). A wide range of secondary issues in routine life can be caused by due to impaired muscles functioning, which can also influence psychosocial aspects such as psychosocial adjustment and quality of life (Gocheva, 2019). Living with chronic disease is stressful and needs effortful adjustment. In a qualitative study with Taiwanese patients, it was noted that living with myasthenia gravis accompanies adjustment with new norm of living with chronic state (Chen, Shih, Hayter, Hou, & Yeh, 2013). There is large amount of published data on muscular diseases that observed the psychological reactions of the chronic illness and concluded that it has adverse effects on patients (Covinsky et al., 1994). Similar to other muscular diseases persons with myasthenia gravis experience great amount of difficulty to perform daily activities and they are required to adjust this chronic state of weakness and fatigability (Kulaksizoglu, 2007). Myasthenia gravis has great impact on every area of life; functional dependency can limit activities such as giving up social activities, hobbies driving and work. chronic neuromuscular disease psychological stressors or daily hassles and stress response can be difficult in terms of patient's ability to adjust (Wallander & Varni, 1998)

Enormous amount of research has focused on etiology, prevalence, and associated disability of myasthenia gravis (Raggi, Leonardi, Mantegazza, Casale, & Fioravanti, 2010). Yet there are few studies that focused on

psychological aspects of the disease. Present study aimed to address impact of disease severity on psychological adjustment of patients with myasthenia gravis.

Subjects and Methods

The research was carried out in June 2020 to April 2021 and it was a correlational cross-sectional study. The data was collected with the support of Pakistan Myasthenia Welfare Organization (PMWO). Sample of the study comprised of N= 270 patients of myasthenia gravis. Of them, 133(52%) were female and 123(48%) were male with overall age range between 20 to 80 years. Patients were approached individually and consent to participate from study was obtained from every patient.

Using purposive sampling technique, the diagnosed patients with myasthenia gravis with duration of disease greater than one year were approached. Patient suffering with any psychiatric comorbidity were excluded from study.

The 8 item myasthenia gravis specific activities of daily living profile developed by Muppidi, (2010) was used, which was developed to assess symptoms of myasthenia gravis and its impact on routine activities, (Muppidi, 2012). Test retest reliability coefficient was 0.93. Items includes chewing, swallowing, talking and breathing, impairment of ability to comb hair and brush teeth, level of difficulty to stand from sitting position, blur or double vision and dropping eyelid. Respondent rated on MG-ADL scale with 4 response options grade 0, grade 1, grade 2 and grade 3 patients have chosen the grade according to the severity of their symptoms. Psychological adjustment scale comprised of 27 items: developed by Sabir, (1999) was used to measure psychological adjustment of myasthenia gravis patients. Patients responded on likert scale with 5 options to respond, options starts from totally wrong (1) to totally right (5). The reliability coefficient of psychological adjustment scale was 0.83.

Prior to administration, MG-ADL was translated into Urdu language through committee approach than through another committee approach it was back translated into English language. To complete the survey questionnaire it took around 15 minutes for each patient. Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS and AMOS.

Results

The MG-ADL scale showed good reliability statistics for all the items, Cronbach's Alpha was 0.835 (Table 1). Factor structure of MG-ADL was evaluated through confirmatory factor analysis using AMOS-24 version. All 8 items had high loadings on their latent factor. The confirmatory analysis resulted in good fit to data. The model reflected an excellent fit to data.

Table 1

Confirmatory Factor Analysis with Factor Loading of Myasthenia Gravis Activities of Daily Living Profile (N=270)

Myasthenia Gravis Activities of Daily Living Profile	Item no.	Loadings
Talking	1	.60
Chewing	2	.54
Swallowing	3	.56
Breathing	4	.64
Impairment of ability to brush teeth or comb hair	5	.61
Impairment of ability to arise from a chair	6	.66
Double Vision	7	.67
Eyelid drop	8	.73

Table showed the CFA of myasthenia gravis activities of daily living profile, loadings of the items are ranged from .54 to .73. In addition, all the factor loadings were found above the criteria (>.35). The results revealed that MG-ADL is statically a valid scale.

Figure.1 Standardized factor loadings in confirmatory factor analysis of MG-ADL disease severity profile AMOS-24

Table 2

Fit Indices of CFA for Myasthenia Gravis Activities of Daily Living Profile (N=270)

Scale	χ^2	df	IFI	NFI	CFI	RMSEA
MG-ADL Profile	51.755	18	.95	.92	.95	.08

Note. χ^2 = Chi-square, df = Degree of freedom, IFI = Incremental fit index, NFI = Normed fit index, CFI = Comparative fit index, RMSEA = Root mean square error of approximation.

Table 3

Reliability Alpha Coefficient of MG-ADL profile

Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient	No of Items
0.835	8

Note. The above table illustrates the reliability measurement Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient for MG-ADL scale. The value of Alpha coefficient 0.835 indicates the measurement is suitable for the target population.

Table 4

Impact of disease severity on psychological adjustment (N= 270)

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable Psychological Adjustment (PAS)
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Disease Severity (MG-ADL)	-0.869***
R ²	.19
	63.40
	0.000

Note: *** mean $p < .001$

The coefficient of disease severity was negative and significant ($\beta = -0.869$, $p < 0.001$) (table 4) which shows that the impact of disease severity on psychological adjustment is negative and significant, decreasing the symptom

severity will enhance the psychological adjustment. The regression analysis explain a total of .19 % variance ($R^2 = .19$) in psychological adjustment.

Discussion

The Present research was carried out to see the impact of disease severity on psychological adjustment of individuals having myasthenia gravis, and core objective of the study was to translate myasthenia gravis disease specific scale MG-ADL in Urdu to measure the impact of symptom severity of myasthenia gravis on psychological health of MG patients. The MG-ADL measures symptom severity in myasthenia gravis patients and its impact on daily living, and have well established psychometric properties. Our results are consistent with literature suggesting good reliability of MG-ADL (Muppidi et al., 2011). Results of the CFA of MG-ADL confirmed the factor validity of measure. In clinical and research settings it is recommended to use MG-ADL to assess patient's symptoms.

The chronic and disabling condition has the potential to effect the psychological adjustment of MG patients. However, there was no study that has systematically investigated the relationship between myasthenia gravis symptom severity and psychological adjustment of the patients. Results of the current study confirm our hypothesis that there is a negative relationship between disease severity and psychological adjustment in patients with myasthenia gravis. A significant association of MG was found with psychiatric comorbidity and psychological adjustment in previous study (Law, Flaherty, & Bandyopadhyay, 2020). It is well documented in existing literature that emotional problems and maladjustment in relation to physical difficulties are linked with the diagnosis of MG and routine frustrations in MG and disease severity caused poor adjustment and emotional distress (Burns, Conaway, Cutter, & Sanders, 2008). The finding of our research are also consistent with the findings formerly reported in literature addressing the influence of myasthenia gravis symptom severity on psychological health of the patients, it was found that change in MGII scores as the outcome variable and variation in depression score and age predicted the change in disease severity in linear regression model (Bogdan et al., 2020). Our results support findings reported by Wallander and Varni that disease severity is a risk factor of psychological adjustment in chronic illness (Wallander & Varni, 1998). Our findings are in line with research that disease severity is associated with maladjustment in chronic diseases (Malik & Koot, 2009). The impact of myasthenia gravis is multidimensional often affecting physical status, psychological well-being and occupational or social consequences (Paul & Gilchrist, 2003).

Conclusion

For assessing symptoms of myasthenia gravis, the Urdu translation of MG-ADL appears as an effective measure. The MG-ADL is ready to be used as routine clinical management and research measure and it appears as a reliable and valid scale. Disease severity of myasthenia gravis has negative impact on psychological adjustment of the MG patients. Mental and psychological health should be a primary focus of the clinicians.

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